

Prescribing Cartesian stiffness of soft robots by co-optimization of shape and physical stiffness

Francesco Stella^{1,2}, Josie Hughes², Daniela Rus³, Cosimo Della Santina^{1,4}

Abstract—Soft robots aim to revolutionize how robotic systems interact with the environment thanks to their inherent compliance. Some of these systems are even able to modulate their physical softness. However, simply equipping a robot with softness will not generate intelligent behaviors. Indeed, most interaction tasks require careful specification of the compliance at the interaction point; some directions must be soft and others firm (e.g., while drawing, entering a hole, tracing a surface, assembling components). On the contrary without careful planning, the preferential directions of deformation of a soft robot are not aligned with the task. With this work, we propose a strategy to prescribe variations of the physical stiffness and the robot’s posture so to implement a desired Cartesian stiffness and location of the contact point. We validate the algorithm in simulation and with experiments. To perform the latter, we also present a new tendon-driven soft manipulator, equipped with variable-stiffness segments and proprioceptive sensing and capable to move in 3D. We show that, combining the intelligent hardware with the proposed algorithm, we can obtain the desired stiffness at the end-effector over the workspace.

I. INTRODUCTION

Inspired by the dexterous environmental interactions show by animals, the inclusion of soft or compliant structure is being mirrored in robotic systems [1] [2]. Animals performance and adaptability in behaviour not only arises from their softness, but from their ability to vary their compliance through postural or physical changes [3]. For example, an elephant trunk shows low stiffness when compliantly exploring the environment, but it stiffens when pulling branches from a tree. It is therefore not surprising that much attention has been given at the design of soft segments with the ability to vary the physical stiffness [4]–[7]. These sophisticated mechanical solutions, allow for modulation of physical stiffness at the physical segment level opposed to with reference to the task space. While for some applications generically changing the physical stiffness may be enough, for some tasks such as drawing, entering a hole, tracing a surface or assembling components, being able to control the Cartesian stiffness is pivotal.

Yet, much of the research focus has been so far confined to developing hardware platforms and algorithmic results relatively limited [8]. In [9], the authors propose an algorithm to select the configuration of the robot so to optimize an overall stiffness index, while solving the inverse kinematic problem. In [10], the Cartesian stiffness of a soft robot is controlled with redundant, torque-controlled, tendon actuation. However, no

Fig. 1. Pictorial representation of the soft robot with variable stiffness proposed in this work, achieving the control goal. Inserting a peg inside a hole is a complex task that requires precision in positioning the peg and creates directional stiffness - stiffer in the plane of the hole, softer in the orthogonal direction. The algorithm we propose can specify low-level actions referred to the body to achieve the desired position and Cartesian stiffness ellipsoid.

algorithm has been proposed that can independently prescribe position and stiffness of the end-effector of a continuum soft robotic system by modulating its physical characteristics.

Thus, the goal of this work is to develop and experimentally test for the first time a model-based algorithm that solves such a challenge. The algorithm takes advantage of soft robot’s redundancy and of novel variable stiffness capabilities by co-optimizing null-space motions and physical stiffness. This is achieved by formulating the problem as a nonlinear optimization, that we break down in two hierarchical sub-problems, one convex and one non-convex. The first problem can be solved efficiently, making it feasible to attack the second via an evolutionary algorithm. We specifically focus on discretized soft robotic continuum body structures as shown in Figure 1. We demonstrate the algorithm with simulations, and with experiments on a novel robot with variable stiffness, showing how the stiffness and position control allows the robot to both exploit high compliance states to conform to the environment, yet show high directional stiffness when needed to achieve specific tasks.

In summary, this paper contributes to the state of the art in

¹Department of Cognitive Robotics, Delft University of Technology, Delft, The Netherlands. ²CREATE Lab, EPFL, Lausanne, Switzerland. ³Computer Science and Artificial Intelligence Laboratory, MIT, Boston, USA. ⁴Institute of Robotics and Mechatronics, German Aerospace Center (DLR), Wessling, Germany. Contact emails: francesco.stella@epfl.ch, josie.hughes@epfl.ch, c.dellasantina@tudelft.nl.

motor intelligence of continuum soft robots by:

- clarifying the analytical model of the relation between Cartesian and structural stiffness, extending existing models for rigid and articulated robots to the case of continuum soft robots,
- developing a novel algorithm that allows to find the stiffness at the joint and the pose of a generic manipulator so to have the desired Cartesian stiffness and position at the end effector,
- demonstrating the first experimental validation of desired Cartesian stiffness in continuum soft robots.

In the remainder of this paper we first present a review of state of the art techniques in variable stiffness soft robot designs and on control methods for Cartesian stiffness control, hence we propose the analytical model for the relationship between Cartesian and structural stiffness for soft robot systems, and the algorithms that allow control of these two attributes. Simulation results are shown to validate these methods, incorporating segment-wise variable stiffness. We next show the design and validation of this robot before presenting results demonstrating the effectiveness of the algorithms developed. We finish with a conclusion and discussion on the developed methods.

II. STATE OF THE ART

We already discussed the state of the art directly related to the main proposed innovation in the introduction. Yet, to achieve these goals, we had to achieve two further secondary innovations that we wish to detail here.

A. Soft variable stiffness mechanisms

There has been much exploration on the mechanical design of single soft segments equipped with variable stiffness capabilities and the control of these VSMS at a mechanism [11], or individual segment level [12]. Some of the most popular techniques used to obtain soft structures with variable stiffness capabilities includes layer [7] and particle [5] jamming, antagonistic pneumatic actuation [6], tensegrity structures [13], mechanisms that exploit the isothermal phase change between liquid and solid state of waxes [14] and metals [15] and passive compliant structures with torque-controlled redundant cable actuation [10]. However, each technology comes with its own limitations. Jamming mechanisms, tensegrity structures and mechanisms based on the thermal phase change of materials allow only for discrete changes in stiffness, resulting in an overall soft or stiff behaviour of the element [16]. Antagonistic pneumatic actuation [17] allows instead for continuous variations in stiffness at the cost of an actuation affected by the dynamics of the air [18], thus requiring extremely accurate modeling of the system [19] to control the stiffness at a joint level [20].

Despite the variety of VSM technologies, it remains a challenge to achieve a multi-segment soft manipulator where the shape and the stiffness of each segment is decoupled and the stiffness can be controlled in a continuous manner. This paper presents and validate experimentally the first system with these characteristics, which is pivotal beyond the present paper to deploy control algorithms and perform complex operations.

B. Cartesian stiffness control in robotics

Analytical models that map the joint stiffness into Cartesian stiffness were first developed for rigid manipulators by Salisbury [21]. The concept has been expanded into Cartesian impedance control algorithms for rigid manipulators [22], [23], with a particular focus on redundant designs [24]–[26] and parallel manipulators [27], [28]. For rigid robots, approaches include those focusing on control of the joint virtual-stiffness [29] or on the pose of the manipulator [30]. More recently, similar formulations have been proposed for structures composed of rigid bodies connected by compliant joints. Within this area, the relation between the stiffness at the joints and the Cartesian stiffness has been analyzed for passive structures with fixed stiffness at the joint [31] and for robots with VSMS at the joints [32]. A methodological evaluation of the Cartesian control possibilities for articulated soft structures is provided by Albu-Schaffer *et al.* [33] In this work, the problem of finding the joints stiffness and configuration to generate a desired Cartesian stiffness and position is formulated as a non-convex optimization problem, solved with a grid search on the joint space. Petit *et al.*, [32], showed that, by removing the constraint on the end effector position, the problem can be rewritten as a convex problem on the stiffness. For the first time, with our algorithm we propose a method to solve the general problem defined by [33] considering both the stiffness and the position for articulated soft structures. This is achieved by leveraging the convex formulation on the stiffness in [32], while exploiting the topology of the nullspace manifold to find the optimal soft robot configuration via an evolutionary algorithm. This new algorithm could be potentially used also in more classic systems with articulated variable stiffness actuators (VSA).

III. CONTROLLING CARTESIAN STIFFNESS THROUGH POSTURE AND PHYSICAL STIFFNESS MODULATION

In this section we aim at developing an algorithm to control the position and stiffness of a soft robot with variable stiffness capabilities at the end effector. To develop it, we introduce an analytical model connecting the physical stiffness and the robot posture to the Cartesian stiffness at the end effector, formulating the discussed challenge in mathematical terms. Finally, we propose the main theoretical contribution of the work: an algorithmic solution to this challenge.

A. Mechanical model

In this subsection, we start by formalizing the relationship between the Cartesian stiffness, defined as the relation between the Cartesian wrench f_{ext} and the Cartesian displacement Δx [21], and the physical stiffness. We do that by extending established results from the articulated soft robotic case [34] to the case of continuum soft robots with variable stiffness.

In [8], Della Santina *et al.* define the general equation of motion for a generic discretized dynamic model a continuum soft body robot with variable stiffness in contact with the environment. In this work we consider the robot to be close to a static equilibrium. Thus we impose the quasi-static conditions

Fig. 2. As an example, we show here a PCC discretization of a soft robot with variable stiffness capabilities. The angles θ_i in the picture are the local curvatures, but in general could represent any collection of strains or weights in a functional representation. A soft robot equipped with VSMs can control the stiffness of sections of its body, σ describes this further degree of actuation. S_i labels the coordinate frames at the end of the i -th segment.

$\ddot{q} \simeq 0$ and $\dot{q} \simeq 0$. Under this assumption, the equation of motion for a generic robot becomes

$$K(q, \sigma) + G(q) - A(q)\tau_{\text{Act}} = J(q)^\top f_{\text{ext}}, \quad (1)$$

where $q \in \mathbb{R}^n$ are the Lagrangian coordinates that define the configuration state of the robot, and \dot{q}, \ddot{q} are their time derivatives. $\sigma \in \mathbb{R}^w$ is the set of coordinates that regulate the stiffness at the joints through an invertible function $k_q = g(\sigma)$. Therefore σ denotes the control input of the VSM, which allows the robot to change the stiffness of its structure. $G(q) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the gravitational force. $K(q, \sigma)$ is the elastic force, with $\frac{\partial K(q, \sigma)}{\partial q} \succ 0 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$, i.e. the stiffness matrix is positive definite. Finally, J represents the manipulator Jacobian $J(q) = \frac{\partial f(q)}{\partial q}$, where $f(q)$ is the forward kinematics mapping, which defines the point contact between the manipulator and the environment as a function of q . In the following we will consider this point to be the end-effector of the robot, without losing generality. Finally, the robot interacts with the environment through an external wrench f_{ext} applied at the end effector. For the sake of generality we consider the case in which the torques are not directly collocated at the joints coordinates, such that there is an intermediate mapping $A(q)$ between the actuation torques τ_{Act} and the torques on the states τ_q .

In the following we consider the assumption that:

- A1 The external forces do not displace the the end-effector significantly. Thus we can impose the displacement in Cartesian space Δx due to external forces is small, i.e. $\Delta x \simeq 0$.

We can now define the physical stiffness λ in configuration space as the derivative of the the external generalized forces with respect to position state q , i.e.

$$\lambda = \frac{d(J(q)^\top f_{\text{ext}})}{dq}. \quad (2)$$

From (1) and (2), it follows that

$$\lambda = \frac{dK(q)}{dq} + \frac{dG(q)}{dq} - \frac{d(A(q)\tau_{\text{Act}})}{dq}, \quad (3)$$

By expanding the terms in (2), the definition of physical stiffness can be rewritten as,

$$\lambda = \frac{dJ^\top}{dq} f_{\text{ext}} + J^\top \frac{df_{\text{ext}}}{dq} = \frac{dJ^\top}{dq} K_x \Delta x + J^\top K_x J. \quad (4)$$

Under assumption A1, (4) can be simplified into

$$\lambda = +J^\top K_x J. \quad (5)$$

The inverse mapping \mathcal{M} that maps the configuration stiffness to Cartesian stiffness $K_x = \mathcal{M}(\lambda)$ can be then solved by considering compliance matrices, which are the inverses of the stiffness matrices ($C_x = K_x^{-1}$ and $C_J = \lambda^{-1}$). Following the same process as above, it is possible to find the relation:

$$C_x = J(q)C_J J(q)^\top, \quad (6)$$

which when rewritten in terms of stiffnesses, becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} K_x &= (J(q)\lambda^{-1}J(q)^\top)^{-1} = J(q)^{\top+} \lambda J(q)^+ = \quad (7) \\ &= J(q)^{\top+} \left(\frac{dK(q, \sigma)}{dq} + \frac{dG(q)}{dq} - \frac{dA(q)\tau_{\text{Act}}}{dq} \right) J(q)^+. \quad (8) \end{aligned}$$

where J^+ represents the pseudo-inverse of the Jacobian matrix.

B. Problem statement

Based on these relations, we propose an algorithm that, given a goal Cartesian position $\bar{x} \in \mathbb{R}^r$, and a desired Cartesian stiffness matrix $\bar{K}_x \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$, finds the optimal joint position $q_{\text{opt}} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and the joint stiffness $k_q = g(\sigma_{\text{opt}}) \in \mathbb{R}^n$. These are optimized so to minimize the error respect to \bar{K}_x under the constraints $\bar{x} = f(q_{\text{opt}})$ and lower and upper bounds on joint stiffness σ and q , as formalized in (10). In particular, the algorithm is developed for redundant robots, i.e. robots in which $r > n$, so to exploit the Nullspace $\mathcal{N} \in \mathbb{R}^{r-n}$ of configurations that satisfy the constraint on the end effector position.

C. Proposed Solution

The following algorithm is developed for a scenario in which the gravity is compensated, and the actuation matrix $A(q)$ is considered constant. Under these assumptions, (8) can be rewritten as:

$$K_x = J(q)^{\top+} \left(\frac{dK(\sigma)}{dq} \right) J(q)^+. \quad (9)$$

As computing $J(q)^+$ can be analytically challenging and computationally expensive [35], it is better to solve the inverse problem in terms of compliances using the relationship given in (6). Due to the non surjective mapping between joint and Cartesian stiffnesses, in general a perfect solution can not be found [36]. Therefore, the general problem is best formulated as a non-convex optimization problem on the physical stiffness

vector σ and on the pose q

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\substack{q \in R^n, \sigma \in R^w}} & \|\overline{C_x} - J(q)C_J(\sigma)J(q)^\top\|_{\text{Fr}} \\ \text{s.t.} & \overline{x} - f(q) = 0 \\ & l_{\text{bound}} \leq q \leq u_{\text{bound}} \\ & l_{\text{bound}} \leq \sigma \leq u_{\text{bound}}, \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where $\|\cdot\|_{\text{Fr}}$ is the Frobenius norm.

However, it is possible to notice that finding the optimal stiffness for a fixed configuration \tilde{q} which satisfies the constraint $\overline{x} - f(\tilde{q}) = 0$ is a convex problem in the Riemannian manifold on the stiffness vector σ . Indeed, the optimal stiffness value for \tilde{q} can be found by solving the more efficient convex optimization problem for the compliance of the VSM. This compliance can be represented as a vector $c_q(\sigma)$ created from the element-wise inversion of the stiffness value of the VSM $k_q(\sigma)$. The optimal stiffness can then be found at the extremes of the cost function $\|\overline{C_x} - J(\tilde{q})C_J(\sigma)J(\tilde{q})^\top\|_{\text{Fr}}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\sigma \in R^w} & C_q^\top H(\tilde{q}, \overline{C_x})C_q + b(\tilde{q}, \overline{C_x})^\top C_q \\ \text{s.t.} & l_{\text{bound}} \leq c_q \leq u_{\text{bound}}, \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where

$$H = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial c_q^2} |\overline{C_x} - JC_q J^\top|_{\text{Fr}} \quad (12)$$

$$b = \frac{\partial}{\partial c_q} |\overline{C_x} - JC_q J^\top|_{\text{Fr}, c_q=0}. \quad (13)$$

which converges on average in 0.021 s for small sized problems. This extremely efficient method for identifying the optimal joint stiffness can now be used as a sub-procedure to perform the non convex optimization step for the nullspace of the robot.

In order to move efficiently in the manifold defined by $\overline{x} - f(q) = 0$, i.e. the nullspace \mathcal{N} of the robot, it is important to develop a tool to project a random configuration on to the manifold. This can be achieved through Algorithm 1, which uses gradient descent with the update $\Delta q_{i+1} = -J^\top(JJ^\top)^{-1}\Delta x(q_i)$ to project a initial random configuration q_0 into a configuration $q \in \mathcal{N}$. Note that in [37], it is proved that the projection operator covers the whole constraint manifold. That is, for any configuration on the manifold, there exist configurations within the ambient space that will be projected onto the configuration.

Algorithm 1 Projection on manifold

```

while true do
  Δx ← Displacement From Constraint(q)
  if |Δx| ≤ ε then
    return q
  end
  J ← EvaluateJacobian(q)
  Δq ← J⊤(JJ⊤)-1Δx
  q ← (q - Δq)
end

```

Once the initial random position is projected on the manifold \mathcal{N} , it is possible to create a local orthonormal basis $\Phi(q)$ for the tangent space to the manifold, i.e. reconstructing the Atlas of the manifold. An orthonormal basis [38] can be created by finding a solution to:

$$\begin{pmatrix} J(q) \\ \Phi(q)^\top \end{pmatrix} \Phi(q) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ I \end{pmatrix}, \quad (14)$$

that is finding the kernel of the Jacobian. **Note that with this step we are approximating the Nullspace of the robot with a plane that is locally tangent to the \mathcal{N} manifold.** Hence a random point q_u can be computed starting from the chart $C_q = (q, \Phi(q))$ as:

$$q_u = q + \Phi(q)u_q, \quad (15)$$

where u_q is a vector that defines a random step that lies on the tangent space $\Phi(q)$. Note that q_u will be close to the manifold but still must be projected to \mathcal{N} . Hence q_u is projected on the manifold \mathcal{N} *orthogonally* to the tangent space of C_J in which it is embedded. The projected configuration q_m is found by solving the system:

$$\begin{cases} \overline{x} - f(q_m) = 0 \\ \Phi(q)^\top (q_m - q) = 0 \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

with a gradient descent method. In Algorithm 2, the following equations are used in the descent:

$$A_u(q_m) = \begin{pmatrix} J(q_m) \\ \Phi(q)^\top \end{pmatrix}, \quad b_u(q_m) = \begin{pmatrix} \overline{x} - f(q_m) \\ \Phi(q)^\top (q_m - q_u) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (17)$$

Algorithm 2 Perpendicular Projection algorithm

Input: q_u

Output: q_m

```

q_m ← q_u
b ← b_u(q_m)
while |b|2 > ε do
  q_m ← q_m - A_u(q_m)-1b
  b ← b_u(q_m)
  if |b|2 ≤ ε then
    return q_m
  end
end

```

By iterating Algorithm 2 it is possible to walk on the manifold i.e. move between adjacent configurations which satisfy the

Fig. 3. **Left image:** Schematics of the optimization algorithm. First a random populations of configurations is generated, then they are projected into configuration with the end effector in the desired position and the optimal stiffness for the chambers is computed for each of the configurations. Finally the error on the Cartesian stiffness is computed. In the next generation, some mutations of the best performing individua are computed through Algorithm 2 and more random configurations are added to have a better covering of the space.

Right image: Convergence of the genetic algorithm over the generations, with an average convergence time of 44 s on an Intel i7 processor.. The best performer is reported with a dotted line, while the mean fitness value of the whole population at the i -th generation is shown with a continuous line. In the bottom-right it is possible to see some of the best performing poses over the computation, where the color of the structure represents the stiffness of the VSM. Finally, the green ellipsoid represents the desired Cartesian stiffness, while the blue ellipsoid represents the Cartesian stiffness achieved by the soft manipulator. The difference between the two decreases over the computation.

constraints imposed on the end effector position.

Given Algorithms 1 and 2, we propose to optimize on the manifold by developing a genetic algorithm (GA) that moves only on the nullspace \mathcal{N} , as schematized in Figure 3. This uses a GA where the population of configurations from the whole joint space is projected to \mathcal{N} through Algorithm 1. For each of these configurations $\in \mathcal{N}$, it is possible to efficiently compute the optimal stiffness through the convex optimization problem described in (11). The performance p of each configuration is evaluated as the Frobenius norm between the desired stiffness and the stiffness ellipsoid obtained by the solution of (11), i.e

$$p = \left(\sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=1}^3 (\overline{C}_{x_{i,j}} - J(\bar{q})_{i,j} C_{J_{i,j}} J^T(\bar{q})_{i,j})^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}. \quad (18)$$

In each iteration of the GA new individuals are added using Algorithm 1 in order to better cover \mathcal{N} , and children are generated using Algorithm 2 to further explore the zones with the best performing configurations. In Figure 3 it is possible to notice that the population converges toward better performing individuals over the computation. The evolutionary algorithm has been integrated in the framework provided by the Matlab Global Optimization toolbox, with the custom functions described in Algorithms 1 and 2 implemented using the Matlab Symbolic toolbox. The parameters used in the GA are: population size equal to 100, mutation rate equal to 0.02 and maximum number of generations equal to 100. Note that,

with this implementation, the computational time required for Algorithm 2 to converge to a solution would not allow the deployment of a Cartesian stiffness and pose controller in real-time. Finally, the pose with the smallest error between the desired and achieved stiffness is chosen.

D. Simulations

In this section we aim to quantify the performance of the achieved stiffness optimized via (10).

The algorithm presented in Section III.B has been implemented in Matlab 2019 and is here evaluated on a soft manipulator discretized with 6 DOFs, describing constant curve arcs in a 3D space, as shown in Figure 3. In the following analysis, the position of the end effector is set, while the orientation is not constrained. This allows us to evaluate the role played by nullspace optimization on the performance of the algorithm. The optimization problem defined in Eq 10, was solved with the end effector goal position being a point of a grid covering the whole the workspace of the continuum manipulator and for two different \overline{K}_x with different direction of the eigenvalues, as shown in Figure 4.

In order to evaluate independently the role of the optimization on the pose q and the stiffness σ on the performance, the error of the optimal configuration is computed for the cases in which the optimization is run only on the nullspace, only on the physical stiffness and on both together. Hence, the error is normalized using the technique presented in [39], in which the concept of stiffability is introduced as a tool to

Fig. 4. **Left image:** stiffability map for different desired stiffness orientations and optimization criteria. **Left:** the result of the optimization with both variable stiffness and nullspace freedom. **Center:** the error heatmap in which only nullspace optimization is considered, and the stiffness of each chamber is kept constant. **Right:** the heatmap in which only the optimization on the stiffness is considered, while the pose is kept constant. **Right image:** reachability map. Thanks to the reachability map we can have an empirical measure of the amplitude of the nullspace inside the workspace. The red rectangle highlights the section of the workspace used for the optimization evaluation.

understand the effects of the optimization parameters on the reachable stiffness for varying positions in the workspace. To be able to compare results with different stiffness amplitudes and orientations, we use the normalized Forbenius norm

$$E_k = \frac{\|\overline{K_x} - K_{\text{opt}}\|_{\text{Fr}}}{\|\overline{K_x}\|_{\text{Fr}}}, \quad (19)$$

where K_{opt} indicates the Cartesian stiffness obtained as with the posture and physical stiffness found solving the optimization problem. The normalization provides the relative deviation from the desired stiffness value. A value of $E_k = 0$ means perfect tracking, with a value of $E_k = 1$ meaning error of the magnitude of the desired stiffness values arise. Firstly, in Figure 4, it is possible to notice that, with the optimization method described in Section III-C, which combines the VSM and Nullspace optimization, we achieve good performances over the workspace (mean(E_k) = 0.33, std(E_k) = 0.46). Moreover, it is possible to evaluate the effects of the VSM and of the nullspace search on the performance individually. Interestingly, when optimizing only between the configurations $\in \mathcal{N}$, the average performance is better than if we optimize only the VSM for fixed configurations. Moreover, if we optimize only on the configurations $\in \mathcal{N}$ the optimization performance is worse in zones where the nullspace is smaller, as shown in the right part of Figure 4, which means that the reachability map [40] and stiffability map are positively correlated.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL PLATFORM: A NEW SOFT ROBOT WITH CONTROLLABLE VARIABLE STIFFNESS

In order to experimentally validate the robustness of the algorithm, we developed a modular structure able to tune its stiffness continuously and to control its configuration independently. In this section we will first introduce the design of a single module. Secondly we will present the integration of

multiple modules for building a robot manipulator, which was used as a test-bed for the algorithm.

A. Modular variable stiffness mechanism

Each module, shown in Figure 5, is composed of an elastic chamber constituting the VSM and by two platforms, where the actuation and sensing are stored. The tendon-driven actuation allows controlling the position of 2 DOFs for each module.

The VSM is composed of an elastic chamber that varies the stiffness as a function of the internal pressure. The chamber is built by casting a silicon material (Dragonskin-20) in four stages, as described in Figure 5. The molds are 3D printed so to be easily assemblable and to allow a simple removal of the cured chamber¹. The chamber is composed of a central beam with three longitudinal communicating cavities around. The inner beam withstands most of the loads in the uninflated configuration and limits the deformation in the axial direction, while the chambers, connected through a tube to a pressure source, allow the segment to change its bending stiffness. The bending stiffness can be controlled as a function of the internal pressure, with an increase in stiffness up to the 300% in the operational range with respect to the uninflated case..

In the uninflated state, the external wall is free to bend, without any energy penalty other than its own structural stiffness. On the contrary, when inflated, the external wall of the chamber goes under tension, following the Young-Lagrange equation [41]. The air behaviour, together with the nonlinear stress-strain relation of Dragonskin-20 [5] leads to an increase in bending stiffness of the whole structure when the internal pressure is increased. In Figure 5 it is possible to notice how deformation of the chambers varies with different

¹The CAD model of the mold, together with the rigid platforms constituting the robot, is available at <https://grabcad.com/library/mold-chamber-softmanipulator-1>

Fig. 5. **Left image:** Schematic representation of a single module, highlighting the independence of the tendon driven actuation respect to the VSM. **Central image:** **a)** The first mold, composed of two parts, in green and orange, is assembled, **b)** the Dragonskin-20 is poured and it is left to cure for 4 hours, **c)** the cured Dragonskin-20 is removed from the first mold, and put in a second mold, represented in red, in which some more Dragonskin-20 has been poured. **d)** Finally, the cured chamber can be removed from the mold and attached to the air tube and platforms. **Bottom:** The chamber deflection due to the 50g load at the tip decrease when the internal pressure increase. The tip displacement is smaller when the chamber is fully inflated, i.e. the stiffness of the chamber increases with the internal pressure. **Right image:** technical drawing of the VSM module, showing how the real system is designed to make it easy to assemble.

internal pressures.

B. Characterization and identification

The bending stiffness of the chamber has been evaluated as a function of the internal pressure, i.e. σ , with the results shown in Figure 6. **Note that the stiffness was evaluated without the tendons, as the stiffness would not vary significantly for small displacements around the static equilibrium [42].** A measurement setup, shown in Figure 6, has been developed to evaluate the stiffness of each chamber as a function of the internal pressure. The chamber is deformed by pushing the tip through a load cell (Futek LSB200) embedded on an actuated platform. The position of the platform is measured with a laser sensor (optoNCDT 1420). The internal pressure is measured using a pressure sensor (Gems Pressure Sensor350) connected to the chamber via a tube.

Using this experimental setup the position, pressure data and the force exerted by the chamber on the load cell are collected using a data acquisition board (NI Multi-channel data acquisition module USB-6000). The setup is controlled with a LabView program that saves the data to be captured and controls the position of the motorized platform. Using these results it is possible to approximate at the first order the stiffness of the i -th chamber as a function of the internal pressure σ_i . To do so, we have to transform the force exerted by the tip F_x and the displacement of the tip Δx data into the structural stiffness k_{bending} and $k_{\text{compression}}$. The length of the segment l , the radius of curvature of the segment r and the curvature angle of the chamber θ are related by $l = r\theta$. Therefore, the kinematic relation between the displacement of

the tip and the bending angle $\Delta\theta$ is:

$$\Delta x = r(1 - \cos(\Delta\theta)) = \frac{l}{\Delta\theta}(1 - \cos(\Delta\theta)). \quad (20)$$

For the small displacements used in the experiment ($\Delta\theta \approx 0$), this relation can be approximated with a McLaurin expansion truncated at the second order, which brings to the result

$$\Delta x = \frac{l\Delta\theta}{2}. \quad (21)$$

We can then write the bending stiffness as:

$$k_{\text{bending}} = \frac{\tau_q}{\Delta\theta} = \frac{F_x l^2}{2\Delta x}, \quad (22)$$

where τ_q represents the torque applied to the chamber. By performing a least squares regression on the $\frac{F_x}{\Delta x}$ we can find the first order approximation of the stiffness-pressure relation as a function of the internal pressure σ_i :

$$k_{\text{bending}_i}(\sigma) = k_{p_0} + g(\sigma_i - p_0), \quad (23)$$

where k_{p_0} is the stiffness at the **atmospheric** pressure p_0 and g is the slope of the first order approximation of the stiffness-pressure relation.

Using a structural model of slender beams, we can find the relation between the bending and compression stiffness by solving the system:

$$\begin{cases} k_{\text{compression}} = \frac{3EI_c}{l^3} \\ k_{\text{bending}} = \frac{EI_{xx}}{l} \end{cases}, \quad (24)$$

where E is the **Young's** modulus of the material, and I_c and I_{xx} represents the inertia **moments** respect to the central and radial axes respectively.

Consequently the stiffness of a single module in configuration

Fig. 6. Pressure-stiffness relation as a function of 5 internal pressures. **Left:** force displacement curve over 5 experiments for each pressure level, together with the least square regression. The slope of the curve, representing the bending stiffness, increases with the internal pressure. **Right:** The regression line as presented in Equation 23, where the data points are the stiffnesses for each pressure level. The bending stiffness of the chamber has been evaluated from displacement vs force curves for several internal pressures. The experiment has been repeated five times for each pressure level $P = 1, 1.05, 1.1, 1.15, 1.2$ bar. **Note that, as the pressure inside the chamber can be changed continuously, so can be the physical stiffness.** Finally, the stiffness is evaluated as the slope of the first order regression of the data. **The bending stiffness of each segment has been limited in the range between 20 Nm/rad and 60 Nm/rad in the optimization problem defined in (12).**

space λ can be evaluated as the Hessian of the elastic potential energy:

$$U(\sigma) = \frac{1}{2}k_{\text{bending}}(\sigma)\theta^2 + \frac{1}{2}k_{\text{compression}}(\sigma)l^2 \quad (25)$$

C. Electronics and low-level control

The actuation and sensing is stored into two platform, placed at the extremes of the elastic chamber. Each platform is composed of two concentric circles and three external housings for the motors and IMUs, as shown in Figure 5. The central circle is used as an attachment for the air chamber, while the second circle keeps the electronic wires and the air tubes in place. Each Micro Metal DC motor actuates a tendon, that is connected to the subsequent platform. Each motor is equipped with a 398:1 gearbox, that has been chosen to provide sufficient torque with a reasonable speed range. Finally, each motor is equipped with a quadrature encoder, with 3600 counts per round of the tendon pulley .

Two Arduino Due microcontrollers are used to control the H-bridges and to record data from the encoders, IMUs and pressure sensors data, placed outside from the body of the robot. The encoders and the pressure sensors are connected to digital interrupts on the microcontroller to allow continuous monitoring, while the IMUs data are connected to the Arduinos via an i2c communication. A serial protocol has been developed, to allow communication between the control program running on the PC and the Arduinos. This allows the direction and speed of each motor to be controlled such that a PID controller can be used to set a desired encoder position. **Similarly, the IMUs and pressure data are sent and processed on the PC in real time to allow close loop control on the curvature of each segment** [43]. A block diagram of the electronic architecture is shown in Figure 7.

D. Soft manipulator

To test the algorithm on a real robot, three modules are combined into the design of a soft manipulator with 6 DOFs

Fig. 7. **Top - Left image:** Image of the soft manipulator in an actuated configuration. **Top - Right image:** Picture of the real manipulator in the undeformed configuration. A blue fabric sleeve is placed on top of the manipulator to keep the wiring and tubing in place. **Bottom image:** System architecture of the electronics, showing the connections between the key components and the flow of data through the control system.

and 3 VSMs, shown in Figure 7.

The robot is modeled as a series of three arcs with constant

curvature, i.e. by adopting a PCC model. This assumption has been demonstrated to approximate accurately the behavior of many continuum robots [44], [45], [46], [47] [48], [49]. For each segment the arc of constant curvature can be univocally defined by just three Lagrangian variables, which represent the configuration variables q described in Section III.A for this system. The Lagrangian coordinates of each segment are: the angle of circumference spanned by the segment θ , the angle of the plane containing the arc ϕ , and arc length L .

Consequently, the full pose of the i -th segment can be completely described by the rotation matrix $R_{i-1}^i(\theta, \phi)$ and translation mapping $t_{i-1}^i(\theta, \phi, L)$ [50]:

$$R_{i-1}^i = \begin{bmatrix} C_{\phi_i}^2(C_{\theta_i} - 1) + 1 & S_{\phi_i}C_{\phi_i}(C_{\theta_i} - 1) & C_{\phi_i}S_{\theta_i} \\ S_{\phi_i}C_{\phi_i}(C_{\theta_i} - 1) & S_{\phi_i}^2(C_{\theta_i} - 1) + 1 & S_{\phi_i}S_{\theta_i} \\ -C_{\phi_i}S_{\theta_i} & -S_{\phi_i}S_{\theta_i} & C_{\theta_i} \end{bmatrix} \quad (26)$$

$$t_{i-1}^i = \frac{L}{\theta} [C_{\phi_i}(C_{\theta_i} - 1) \quad S_{\phi_i}(C_{\theta_i} - 1) \quad S_{\theta_i}]^T,$$

with C_{ϕ_i} , C_{θ_i} , S_{ϕ_i} , S_{θ_i} being $\cos(\phi_i)$, $\cos(\theta_i)$, $\sin(\phi_i)$, $\sin(\theta_i)$ respectively.

The two can be combined in a homogeneous transformation mapping from the frame at the bottom of the segment to the frame at the top of the segment as:

$$T_{i-1}^i = \begin{bmatrix} R_{i-1}^i & t_{i-1}^i \\ [0 \ 0 \ 0] & 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (27)$$

where t_{i-1}^i and R_{i-1}^i represent the rotation matrix and the translation mapping the reference frame at the base of the i -th segment to the one attached to its tip. Finally, another advantage of the PCC assumption is that the whole kinematics can be decomposed into two mappings [51]. A first mapping $q = m(h)$ brings from actuator coordinates h , i.e. the length of the tendons to configuration space parameters that describe CC arcs q , and a second mapping $x = f(q) = f(m(h))$ maps the PCC coordinates into Cartesian coordinates.

V. RESULTS

A. Experimental validation

An experiment is performed to merge the analytical results from the optimization with the physical performance of the robot. The robot is commanded to the configuration and physical stiffness found as solution of the algorithm described in Section III-C. The stiffness ellipsoid of the end effector is then evaluated perturbing the soft robot with the robotic manipulator Franka Emika Panda [52] along 6 directions, shown in Figure 8. A representation of the experiment and of the comparison of goal and experimental stiffnesses is shown in Figure 9.

During the experiment, both the displacement of the end effector $\Delta x \in R^{3 \times v}$ and the reaction forces $F \in R^{3 \times v}$ are recorded, with v the number of samples per experiment. Hence, the experimental ellipsoid matrix $K_{\text{exp}} \in R^{3 \times 3}$ evaluated by minimizing the least square error as:

$$K_{\text{Experiment}} = F\Delta x^+. \quad (28)$$

Over 8 experiments, the end-effector stiffness closely matched

Fig. 8. Experiment representation: the soft manipulator, with the configuration and physical stiffness resulting from the optimization, q_{opt} , k_{opt} is perturbed along the x , y and z axes for 4 cm by a second rigid manipulator, attached at the end effector. In the figure it is possible to notice the displacement respect to the unloaded configuration, presented in the central image. During the experiment the position and reaction force of the manipulator are recorded for later postprocessing.

the desired stiffness ellipsoid, with an average error of $E_k = 0.43$.

B. Task-based validation

Thanks to the algorithm presented in Section III-C, the robot is able to complete tasks in which the directional control of the stiffness ellipsoid is crucial, such as inserting a peg in the hole. For assembly tasks that require a tight fit, the robot must be able to be stiff in the direction of the hole, to be able to push the peg inside whilst compliant in the perpendicular plane, so to adjust for misalignments. Therefore we can command the robot to perform a peg insertion by providing only the position of the hole and the desired direction as an input. In Figure 10, it is possible to see the convergence the robot toward the hole over two scenarios. Interestingly, the control scheme has no constraints on the end effector orientation. Moreover, thanks to the embedded softness, the robot is able to comply with unmodeled obstacles, such as the plastic wall in Figure 10.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we present a model based approach to bring Cartesian stiffness control to soft robotics. This method equips soft robots with the ability of actively exploiting their inherent compliance when interacting with the environment.

Firstly, the relations between the structural stiffness and the Cartesian stiffness for a generic soft robot is presented, together with an evolutionary algorithm that allows control of the stiffness and position of the end effector. The optimization is evaluated for a generic 6 DOFs soft manipulator, distinguishing between the performance achieved by the redundancy of the robot and by the variable stiffness mechanisms. Secondly, the design and fabrication of a robotic manipulator with continuously tunable stiffness is discussed. The performance of the algorithm on the robotic platform is studied by experimentally, analyzing the real Cartesian stiffness of the end effector through a second manipulator. Finally, a demonstration on the robot in a real task, i.e. a peg in the hole, is presented.

Fig. 9. **Top:** Images of the real experiments. Here it is possible to notice the rigid manipulator, [52], connected to the soft manipulator. The soft manipulator is in the optimal configuration, as resulting from the optimization algorithm. **Center:** q_{opt} configuration and the optimal stiffness per chamber resulting from the optimization. **The experiment is repeated for 5 different goal positions and stiffnesses.** **Bottom:** comparison of the Goal, Optimal and Experimental stiffness ellipsoid, together with the E_k metric. The robot is able to accurately achieve the desired stiffness at the end effector.

Fig. 10. Thanks to accurate control the robot was able to complete insert a peg in the hole just by knowing the position of the hole and the desired stiffness ellipsoid. **The Cartesian stiffness commanded was designed so to have one eigenvector with the highest eigenvalue parallel to the axe of the hole, and the other eigenvectors placed parallel to the plane of the hole.** Note than no constraints on the end-effector orientation have been given

In contrast with the growing interest on variable stiffness designs, analytical results showed that the performance resulting from an accurate modeling and control of the structure exceeds the performance achievable with VSM tuning only. Future work will be devoted to consider dynamic interactions, i.e. the control of the impedance of the robot based on the physical properties of the soft structure, rather than on the accurate control of external moments.

REFERENCES

- [1] C. Della Santina, M. G. Catalano, and A. Bicchi, "Soft robots," *Encyclopedia of Robotics*, 2020.
- [2] S. Kim, C. Laschi, and B. Trimmer, "Soft robotics: a bioinspired evolution in robotics," *Trends in biotechnology*, vol. 31, no. 5, pp. 287–294, 2013.
- [3] N. Hogan, "Impedance control: An approach to manipulation," in *1984 American control conference*. IEEE, 1984, pp. 304–313.
- [4] S. Wolf, G. Grioli, O. Eiberger, W. Friedl, M. Grebenstein, H. Höppner, E. Burdet, D. G. Caldwell, R. Carloni, M. G. Catalano, *et al.*, "Variable stiffness actuators: Review on design and components," *IEEE/ASME transactions on mechatronics*, vol. 21, no. 5, pp. 2418–2430, 2015.
- [5] T. Ranzani, G. Gerboni, M. Cianchetti, and A. Menciassi, "A bioinspired soft manipulator for minimally invasive surgery," *Bioinspiration & biomimetics*, vol. 10, no. 3, p. 035008, 2015.
- [6] S. M. Babu, A. Sadeghi, A. Mondini, and B. Mazzolai, "Antagonistic pneumatic actuators with variable stiffness for soft robotic applications," in *International Conference on Soft Robotics (RoboSoft)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 283–288.
- [7] Y.-J. Kim, S. Cheng, S. Kim, and K. Iagnemma, "A novel layer jamming mechanism with tunable stiffness capability for minimally invasive surgery," *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, vol. 29, no. 4, pp. 1031–1042, 2013.
- [8] C. Della Santina, C. Duriez, and D. Rus, "Model based control of soft robots: A survey of the state of the art and open challenges," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2110.01358*, 2021.
- [9] J. M. Bern and D. Rus, "Soft ik with stiffness control," in *4th International Conference on Soft Robotics (RoboSoft)*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 465–471.
- [10] T. Su, L. Niu, G. He, X. Liang, L. Zhao, and Q. Zhao, "Coordinated variable impedance control for multi-segment cable-driven continuum manipulators," *Mechanism and Machine Theory*, vol. 153, p. 103969, 2020.
- [11] F. Maghooa, A. Stilli, Y. Noh, K. Althoefer, and H. A. Wurdemann, "Tendon and pressure actuation for a bio-inspired manipulator based on an antagonistic principle," in *International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)*, 2015, pp. 2556–2561.
- [12] A. Shiva, A. Stilli, Y. Noh, A. Faragasso, I. D. Falco, G. Gerboni, M. Cianchetti, A. Menciassi, K. Althoefer, and H. A. Wurdemann, "Tendon-based stiffening for a pneumatically actuated soft manipulator," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 632–637, 2016.
- [13] D. Zappetti, R. Arandes, E. Ajanic, and D. Floreano, "Variable-stiffness tensegrity spine," *Smart Materials and Structures*, vol. 29, no. 7, p. 075013, 2020.
- [14] N. G. Cheng, A. Gopinath, L. Wang, K. Iagnemma, and A. E. Hosoi, "Thermally tunable, self-healing composites for soft robotic applications," *Macromolecular Materials and Engineering*, vol. 299, no. 11, pp. 1279–1284, 2014.
- [15] W. Shan, T. Lu, and C. Majidi, "Soft-matter composites with electrically tunable elastic rigidity," *Smart Materials and Structures*, vol. 22, no. 8, p. 085005, 2013.
- [16] J. Choi, D.-Y. Lee, J.-H. Eo, Y.-J. Park, and K.-J. Cho, "Tendon-driven jamming mechanism for configurable variable stiffness," *Soft Robotics*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 109–118, 2021.
- [17] M. T. Gillespie, C. M. Best, and M. D. Killpack, "Simultaneous position and stiffness control for an inflatable soft robot," in *International conference on robotics and automation (ICRA)*. IEEE, 2016, pp. 1095–1101.
- [18] M. Stölzle and C. Della Santina, "Piston-driven pneumatically-actuated soft robots: modeling and backstepping control," *IEEE Control Systems Letters*, vol. 6, pp. 1837–1842, 2021.
- [19] Y. Ansari, M. Manti, E. Falotico, M. Cianchetti, and C. Laschi, "Multi-objective optimization for stiffness and position control in a soft robot arm module," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 108–115, 2017.
- [20] C. M. Best, L. Rupert, and M. D. Killpack, "Comparing model-based control methods for simultaneous stiffness and position control of inflatable soft robots," *The International Journal of Robotics Research*, vol. 40, no. 1, pp. 470–493, 2021.
- [21] J. K. Salisbury, "Active stiffness control of a manipulator in cartesian coordinates," in *Conference on decision and control including the symposium on adaptive processes*. IEEE, 1980, pp. 95–100.
- [22] A. Ajoudani, "Exploring the roles of common mode stiffness (cms) and configuration dependent stiffness (cdfs) control," in *Transferring Human Impedance Regulation Skills to Robots*. Springer, 2016, pp. 47–58.
- [23] L. Peternel, N. Beckers, and D. A. Abbink, "Independently commanding size, shape and orientation of robot endpoint stiffness in tele-impedance by virtual ellipsoid interface," in *International Conference on Advanced Robotics (ICAR)*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 99–106.
- [24] E. B. Pitt, N. Simaan, and E. J. Barth, "An investigation of stiffness modulation limits in a pneumatically actuated parallel robot with actuation redundancy," in *Fluid Power Systems Technology*, vol. 57236. American Society of Mechanical Engineers, 2015, p. V001T01A063.
- [25] A. L. Orekhov and N. Simaan, "Directional stiffness modulation of parallel robots with kinematic redundancy and variable stiffness joints," *Journal of Mechanisms and Robotics*, vol. 11, no. 5, p. 051003, 2019.
- [26] J. J. Rice and J. M. Schimmels, "Passive compliance control of redundant serial manipulators," *Journal of Mechanisms and Robotics*, vol. 10, no. 4, p. 044507, 2018.
- [27] A. Pashkevich, A. Klimchik, S. Caro, and D. Chablat, "Cartesian stiffness matrix of manipulators with passive joints: analytical approach," in *2011 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*. IEEE, 2011, pp. 4034–4041.
- [28] M. F. Metzger, N. A. Faruk Senan, and O. M. O'Reilly, "On cartesian stiffness matrices in rigid body dynamics: an energetic perspective," *Multibody System Dynamics*, vol. 24, no. 4, pp. 441–472, 2010.
- [29] C. Ott, *Cartesian impedance control of redundant and flexible-joint robots*. Springer, 2008.
- [30] A. Ajoudani, N. G. Tsagarakis, and A. Bicchi, "On the role of robot configuration in cartesian stiffness control," in *2015 IEEE international conference on robotics and automation (ICRA)*. IEEE, 2015, pp. 1010–1016.
- [31] N. Ciblak and H. Lipkin, "Synthesis of cartesian stiffness for robotic application," vol. 3, 02 1999, pp. 2147 – 2152 vol.3.
- [32] F. Petit and A. Albu-Schäffer, "Cartesian impedance control for a variable stiffness robot arm," in *2011 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*. IEEE, 2011, pp. 4180–4186.
- [33] A. Albu-Schäffer, M. Fischer, G. Schreiber, F. Schoeppe, and G. Hirzinger, "Soft robotics: what cartesian stiffness can obtain with passively compliant, uncoupled joints?" in *2004 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)(IEEE Cat. No. 04CH37566)*, vol. 4. IEEE, 2004, pp. 3295–3301.
- [34] C. Della Santina, M. Catalano, and A. Bicchi, "Soft robots," *Springer Encyclopedia of robotics*, 2021.
- [35] C. Della Santina, A. Bicchi, and D. Rus, "On an improved state parametrization for soft robots with piecewise constant curvature and its use in model based control," *IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 1001–1008, 2020.
- [36] A. Albu-Schäffer and G. Hirzinger, "Cartesian impedance control techniques for torque controlled light-weight robots," in *Proceedings 2002 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (Cat. No. 02CH37292)*, vol. 1. IEEE, 2002, pp. 657–663.
- [37] Z. Kingston, M. Moll, and L. E. Kavraki, "Exploring implicit spaces for constrained sampling-based planning," *The International Journal of Robotics Research*, vol. 38, no. 10-11, pp. 1151–1178, 2019.
- [38] W. C. Rheinboldt, "Manpak: A set of algorithms for computations on implicitly defined manifolds," *Computers & Mathematics with Applications*, vol. 32, no. 12, pp. 15–28, 1996.
- [39] F. Petit, "Analysis and control of variable stiffness robots," Ph.D. dissertation, ETH-Zürich, 2014.
- [40] F. Zacharias, C. Borst, and G. Hirzinger, "Capturing robot workspace structure: representing robot capabilities," in *2007 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems*. Ieee, 2007, pp. 3229–3236.
- [41] I. Müller and P. Strehlow, *Rubber and rubber balloons: paradigms of thermodynamics*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2004, vol. 637.

- [42] K. Oliver-Butler, J. Till, and C. Rucker, "Continuum robot stiffness under external loads and prescribed tendon displacements," *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, vol. 35, no. 2, pp. 403–419, 2019.
- [43] J. Hughes, F. Stella, C. D. Santina, and D. Rus, "Sensing soft robot shape using imus: An experimental investigation," in *Experimental Robotics*, B. Siciliano, C. Laschi, and O. Khatib, Eds. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2021, pp. 543–552.
- [44] M. W. Hannan and I. D. Walker, "Kinematics and the implementation of an elephant's trunk manipulator and other continuum style robots," *Journal of robotic systems*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 45–63, 2003.
- [45] N. Simaan, R. Taylor, and P. Flint, "A dexterous system for laryngeal surgery," in *IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation, 2004. Proceedings. ICRA'04. 2004*, vol. 1. IEEE, 2004, pp. 351–357.
- [46] I. S. Godage, D. T. Branson, E. Guglielmino, G. A. Medrano-Cerda, and D. G. Caldwell, "Shape function-based kinematics and dynamics for variable length continuum robotic arms," in *2011 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation*. IEEE, 2011, pp. 452–457.
- [47] E. Milana, F. Stella, B. Gorissen, D. Reynaerts, and C. D. Santina, "Model-based control can improve the performance of artificial cilia," in *2021 IEEE 4th International Conference on Soft Robotics (RoboSoft)*, 2021, pp. 527–530.
- [48] R. K. Katzschmann, C. Della Santina, Y. Toshimitsu, A. Bicchi, and D. Rus, "Dynamic motion control of multi-segment soft robots using piecewise constant curvature matched with an augmented rigid body model," in *2019 2nd IEEE International Conference on Soft Robotics (RoboSoft)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 454–461.
- [49] C. Della Santina, A. Bicchi, and D. Rus, "Dynamic control of soft robots with internal constraints in the presence of obstacles," in *2019 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 6622–6629.
- [50] R. J. Webster III and B. A. Jones, "Design and kinematic modeling of constant curvature continuum robots: A review," *The International Journal of Robotics Research*, vol. 29, no. 13, pp. 1661–1683, 2010.
- [51] B. A. Jones and I. D. Walker, "Kinematics for multisection continuum robots," *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 43–55, 2006.
- [52] F. Emika, "Panda," *tech. rep*, 2018.